

Recent Developments in Zeta-Sandwich/ Plate Structures

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ABSTRACT

The structural concept of the zeta sandwich was first proposed by Miura in 1972, with an intention to obtain a structural form which can compete with the honeycomb sandwich in rigidity-to-weight ratio basis by simpler form. The geometrical core form is derived from a kind of mathematical superposition of two mutually orthogonal corrugations and resulted in a single continuous surface. Principal features of the sandwich are; the high rigidity, the isotropy of the elastic properties, and the possibility of circulating a fluid within the sandwich. Furthermore, it is shown that the combination of a flat plate and a zeta-core as a backing sheet results in a two-dimensionally stiffened plate. Recently, the roll forming process has been successfully developed for manufacturing continuously zeta-core from sheet metals of aluminum alloy and steel. It is still in the stage of laboratory test, however, the principal features in the forming process has been revealed and which can provide the sufficient basis for developing the mass production process.

NOMENCLATURE

a	=area of rhomboidal element	θ	=inclination angle of oblique element
g,h	=periodic functions	μ	=form efficiency of core
l,m,n	=components of unit normal vector	σ	=normal stress
r	=unit vector	τ	=shear stress
t	=uniform thickness of rhomboidal element	ψ	=direction, counter-clockwise from x-axis on x-y plane
U	=strain energy	ω	=zigzag angle of ridge
v	=gross volume between facings filled by fundamental region	Subscripts	
α	=filling factor of core	av	=average
β	=reduction ratio	c	=core property
γ	=shear strain	i	=ith element
ϵ	=normal strain	iso	=isotropic

(Other symbols are explained in the text.)

Fig.1 Sandwich constructions with oblique/perpendicular wall

Fig.2 Geometry of zeta-core

Fig.3 Fundamental region of a zeta-core

EMERGING OF ZETA CORE FORM

From the point of view of structural concept, the excellent characteristic of honeycomb core is distinctly attributable to its stabilized perpendicular wall elements in proper orientation and distribution. This observation raises a question whether the wall elements should necessarily be perpendicular to facings. Since there is no reason why the question is to be answered in the affirmative, the possibility of a core having oblique wall elements cannot be excluded.

To obtain a key to the solution of the question, we shall consider a hypothetical core made of nonperpendicular, oblique wall elements as shown in Fig.1a. This core is formed by orthogonally intersecting, in mathematical sense, a pair of v-corrugated sheets so that the crest ridges of the sheets form a square lattice. This is compared with the honeycomb core of square type shown in Fig. 1b, which is assumed to have the identical apparent density with the hypothetical core.

For purposes of comparison, let us calculate the strain energy of each core per unit gross volume when it constitutes a sandwich construction and is subject to a certain amount of plate shear deformation. Within the scope of the approximate membrane stress analysis, the ratio of strain energies of oblique core to perpendicular core is $\sin^2\theta + (\sin^2 2\theta)/2$, where θ is the angle between oblique walls and facings. Apparently this value slightly exceeds 1 for $\pi/4 < \theta < \pi/2$. Thus it can be concluded that a hypothetical core having oblique wall elements can be more rigid than the honeycomb core. Although manufacturing the hypothetical core is rather difficult, the previous conclusion indicates the potentialities of this kind of core if it can be embodied in some other forms.

During the study of deformation of an infinite plate, the present author has been aware of the existence of the doubly corrugated surface (1,2). It is the surface made by superposing ingeniously two corrugations in mutually orthogonal directions. A typical double corrugation surface can be expressed by the function.

$$z = gyz[y - h_{xy}(x)] \quad (1)$$

Fig.4 Aluminum zeta-core sandwich

where g_{yz} and h_{xy} represent certain continuous, single-valued, bounded, periodic functions defined in $y-z$ and $x-y$ plane, respectively.

At this point, a little insight into the problem will bring us from the configuration of Eq.1 to a configuration shown in Fig.2, which is a real embodiment of the aforementioned hypothetical oblique wall core concept (3,4). Geometrically this surface is constructed by using a truncated zigzag function $g_{yz}(y)$ and a zigzag function $h_{xy}(x)$. It can also be constructed by the repetition of the fundamental region which is composed of four congruent rhomboids and two congruent chevron patterns as shown in Fig.3. In this configuration, it is seen that each rhomboidal element of the sides of corrugations is supported by adjacent elements and facings. Therefore, it provides a stabilized structural component workable under various loading conditions. The diverse orientation of each rhomboidal element can control the macroscopic properties of the sandwich construction either isotropic or orthotropic. In addition, zigzag and interlocking top and bottom parts of the core can provide proper and well distributed bonding zones. The combinations of other functions g and h give many variations in core forms. Thus, a sample of an "zeta-sandwich" is shown in Fig.4.

ELASTIC PROPERTIES OF ZETA-CORE

Among the principal quantities relating to the elastic properties of core, the shear modulus G_C is an important as well as only representative quantity. The shear modulus shall now be calculated analytically. The rectangular coordinates x, y, z are taken so that x and y axes may lie on the facing surface. Further, the direction ψ is defined, which is ψ radian counter-clockwise from x axis on $x-y$ plane. The strains of the core are now considered when the sandwich is subject to a shear deformation $\gamma_{\psi z}$ in $\psi-z$ plane.

First, it is assumed that the facings are infinitely rigid as for both in-plane and bending deformation. Secondly, the presence of the membrane stress state is assumed. Then, for an arbitrary element i (Fig.3), the deformation applied externally from facing is the relative parallel transfer of a pair of edges on facings. Therefore, the first approximation on the strain distribution, which can be compatible with the displacements at facings, is the homogeneity of strain within the element i . If this situation is accepted, the resulting strains in each element are identical to the strains of the identical position

and direction in a hypothetical core made of a homogeneous continuum subjected to the said external displacements.

Now, a normal unit vector $r_{3i}\{l_i, m_i, n_i\}$ is defined on the i th rhomboidal element as shown in Fig.4. Also, a couple of vectors r_{1i} and r_{2i} are defined, r_{1i} on the intersection of the x - y plane and the i th element, r_{2i} vertical to r_{1i} on i th element. The normal strains of the element i are represented by the extensional strains ϵ_{1i} and ϵ_{2i} of the vectors r_{1i} and r_{2i} , respectively.

$$\epsilon_{1i}=0 \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_{2i}=\gamma_{\psi z}(-m_i n_i \sin\psi - l_i n_i \cos\psi) \quad (3)$$

The shear strain γ_{12i} due to $\gamma_{\psi z}$ can be calculated as the shear deformation of two vectors r_{1i} and r_{2i} which were originally perpendicular to each other before deformation.

$$\gamma_{12i}=\gamma_{\psi z}(-l_i \sin\psi + m_i \cos\psi) \quad (4)$$

The total strain energy of the core is a simple summation of the partial strain energy for each element and is given by

$$U=1/2\gamma_{\psi z}^2 \sum_i a_i t_i [G(-l_i \sin\psi + m_i \cos\psi)^2 + E(1-\nu^2)^{-1}(m_i n_i \sin\psi + l_i n_i \cos\psi)^2] \quad (5)$$

where a_i and t_i represent the area and the constant thickness of the element. And the summation is carried out within the fundamental region. Now, the gross volume between facings filled by a fundamental region of a zeta-core is denoted by v . The strain energy U of the hypothetical continuum of the same gross volume v and with the shear modulus G_c , when it is subject to a uniform shear strain $\gamma_{\psi z}$, is $\gamma_{\psi z}^2 v G_c / 2$. Because this must be equal to the Eq.(5), the effective shear modulus of a zeta-core is given by the following formula.

$$G_c=2U/\gamma_{\psi z}^2 v \quad (6)$$

Hereupon the concept of form efficiency of core is introduced that is a dimensionless form of shear modulus defined by

$$\mu=G_c/G_\alpha \quad (7)$$

where G is the shear modulus of the material of core, and α is the spatial filling factor of core. In addition, the following reduction ratio is defined to exclude the flat top (bottom) part of the core from the computation, because this dead volume does not contribute to the strain energy.

$$\beta=[(\text{net volume})-(\text{volume of top \& bottom})]/(\text{net volume}) \quad (8)$$

From Eqs.(5,6,7,and 8) the form efficiency of the zeta-core is given by the following formula.

$$\mu(\psi)=\beta/(\sum_i a_i t_i) \sum_i a_i t_i [G(-l_i \sin\psi + m_i \cos\psi)^2 + E(1-\nu^2)^{-1}(m_i n_i \sin\psi + l_i n_i \cos\psi)^2] \quad (9)$$

In case of the fundamental region of Fig.3, if an appropriate rectangular coordinates x, y, z are chosen like those in the figure, the components of normal unit vectors of four rhomboidal elements composing a fundamental region can be expressed solely by a set of l^*, m^*, n^* , which are assigned to be positive. By this simplified manipulation, Eq.(9) reduces to

$$\mu(\psi)=\beta[(1^*{}^2 + \frac{2m^*{}^2 n^*{}^2}{1-\nu}) \sin^2\psi + (m^*{}^2 + \frac{2l^*{}^2 n^*{}^2}{1-\nu}) \cos^2\psi] \quad (10)$$

Since the design of sandwich constructions is primarily effected by the elastic property of the weakest direction, the isotropy of the core property is generally desirable. In case of the previous example, the circular isotropy

condition is realizable when the following relation is satisfied between components of normal unit vectors of rhomboidal elements,

$$l^{*2} + 2m^{*2}n^{*2} / (1-\nu) = m^{*2} + 2l^{*2}n^{*2} / (1-\nu) \quad (11)$$

thus, by virtue of Eq.(10), the μ value of the core is independent of ψ value. There are two cases that satisfy above relation and these are:

Case I $l^* = m^*$

$$\mu_{iso} = \beta \{ 1/2 + (1+\nu)n^{*2} / [2(1-\nu)] - n^{*4} / (1-\nu) \} \quad (12)$$

Case II $n^* = [(1-\nu)/2]^{1/2}$

$$\mu_{iso} = \beta(1+\nu)/2 \quad (13)$$

In practice, however, it is not necessary to provide a complete isotropy. In view of these, it is preferred to allow a deviation from complete isotropy within the range of $\pm 20\%$. In Fig.5, the inclination angle of element, $\theta = \cos^{-1}n^*$, is plotted on the axis of abscissa, and m^*/l on the axis of ordinate. The combination of l^* , m^* , and n^* which gives complete isotropy is shown by line I where $m^* = l^*$ and line II where $n^* = [(1-\nu)/2]^{1/2}$. Contour line-like curves drawn with these lines as axes show the case of deviation of $\pm 5\%$, $\pm 10\%$, $\pm 15\%$, and $\pm 20\%$ sequentially from the center, and the region which shows a substantial isotropy is shown by the criss-cross region.

As a matter of course, the core desirably has a large μ value besides being isotropic. For example, in case of honeycomb core, the μ value is 0.625 for the ribbon direction and 0.375 for the other principal direction. Provisionally these values can be the target for high strength cores.

It should be noted that in the Case I isotropy configuration, μ value is the function of the component n^* alone. Figure 6 is a graphical representation of μ - n^* relation. The maximum value of μ_{iso} is given by the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{iso} &= \beta \{ 1/2 + (1+\nu) / [16(1-\nu)] \} & \text{at } n^* &= (1+\nu)^{1/2} / 2 \\ &= \beta(2/3) & \text{if } \nu &= 1/3 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

If a typical value of β is assumed to be 0.8, then $\mu_{iso} = 0.533$ for the inclination angle $\theta = \cos^{-1}n^* = 54^\circ 44'$ when $\nu = 1/3$.

Fig.5 Combination of orientation variables which gives isotropic elastic property

Fig.6 Form efficiency-inclination angle relation

If Fig.6 is seen with reference to Fig.5, combinations of l^* , m^* , and n^* and the corresponding μ value are clearly understood. As is seen from Eq. (14), μ/β is maximum at $2/3$ when $n^*=(1+\nu)^{1/2}/2$ ($=1/3^{1/2}$ when $\nu=1/3$). This almost coincides with the conditions for complete isotropy, that is $n^*=[(1-\nu)/2]^{1/2}$ ($=1/3^{1/2}$ when $\nu=1/3$). Generally, the region defined to provide isotropy corresponds with the region having a large μ . In other words, this defined region shows double peaks of the scale of isotropy and the scale of the absolute value of μ .

ZETA-PLATE CONCEPT

There are many examples of uni-directionally stiffened plates, such as ribbed plates, plates stiffened by trapezoidal box ribs or corrugated plates. On the other hand, it is not easy to find appropriate examples of two-dimensionally stiffened plates. The isogrid structure is a rare example of that case which consists of a skin and ribs arranged uniformly in three directions. As the isogrid structure is manufactured by the costly machining process, so the application of the concept is limited to aero/space structures.

In 1978, Miura (5) proposed the zeta-plate concept (or zeta-stiffened panel) as a candidate of the two-dimensionally stiffened plate. The zeta-plate eventually is a combination of a flat plate and a zeta-core as a backing sheet. In order to study the elastic properties of this rather unusual configuration, Tanizawa et al (6) developed a FEM procedure and calculated the equivalent rigidities of a typical zeta-plate, some of the results are shown in the following.

The polar diagram of the equivalent bending rigidity is shown in Fig.7 in the normalized form. The factor for normalization, $EI_m = E \cdot t_m^3/12$, corresponds to the bending rigidity per unit length of the homogeneous isotropic flat plate with the same material and the average thickness t_m . The subscript indicates the value of the quantity at the angle from the x axis.

It is interesting to note that the zeta-plate exhibits almost isotropic behavior in spite of its asymmetric configuration. The bending rigidity is about ten times as high as that of the isotropic homogeneous plate having the same weight per unit area. For comparison purpose, the bending rigidities of an isogrid plate and a plate stiffened by a corrugated sheet ($\omega=90^\circ$) are shown in the same figure. The similar comparison is made about the torsional rigidity and is shown in Fig.8.

Fig.7 Polar diagram of the equivalent bending rigidity

Fig.8 Polar diagram of the equivalent torsional rigidity

The numerical values shown above represents only a single example of the zeta-plate. Actually a sample of a zeta-core is used for the stiffener. Further optimization study, therefore, is needed to establish the basis of this concept.

NEW MANUFACTURING METHOD OF ZETA-CORE

A method using a press has heretofore been proposed to manufacture zeta-core materials. Such a manufacturing method is an extrusion forming which mainly relies upon ductility of a workpiece, in which an increase in surface area of an extruded portion is covered by a decrease in wall thickness of a workpiece of said portion. Therefore, the wave head and wave bottom which are locally large in deformation are liable to result in excessive decrease in wall thickness and breakage. Therefore, a method has been heretofore employed wherein a wave-form protrusion of a die for the press is gradually increased in height from one end to the other to intermittently feed a metal plate pitch by pitch thereby enhancing the machining degree successively to prevent the breakage of material. In such a method, however, the manufacturing device becomes complicated and it is difficult to increase the productivity.

In accordance with the present method, a zeta-core material is formed at one process by male and female forming rolls having the same wave-form as that of the zeta-core. By this process we obtain a forming device having a high productivity without being suffered from those disadvantages as noted above. According to the forming method using rolls, a material has a small portion to be restricted by rolls when it is processed, a folding effect of the material is brought forth at the time of forming, a formed article is shortened with respect to longitudinal and lateral lengths of the material to relieve the extrusion machining through that amount, and continuous forming at one effort is rendered possible.

Fig.9 is a perspective view of one example of a zeta-core, a zigzag vertical angle formed between the wave head and wave bottom being 90°. Material is liable to be broken at the time of forming in the vicinity of zigzag top portions encircled by dotted lines.

In the present method, a roll for forming a zeta-core material from a flat plate such as metal is formed with forming tooth-forms associated with the surface of the roll in a zigzag fashion which shows only the wave head in Fig.10. There are a lateral type forming roll in which forming tooth-forms are continuous in an axial direction of the roll as shown in Fig.10a and a longitudinal forming roll in which forming tooth-forms are continuous in a peripheral direction of the roll as shown in Fig.10b. The lateral type forming roll is more realistic than the other in terms of fabrication as will be described hereinafter.

A material may be passed through between the pair of forming rolls as described to thereby continuously form a zeta-core material at one effect. In this forming method, such formation seems to be rendered possible because a restricted portion by the rolls is small, a shrinkage of length about 10 to 30% is appeared in the lengthwise direction of the material at the time of machining, and extrusion machining is relieved through that amount. However, it is still desirable to slightly round off corners of the forming tooth-forms.

If forming is accomplished with the depth of action between the forming rolls made to be shallow, as described above, the wave head and the wave bottom of the wave-form of the zeta-core material are curved to fail to provide a plane. Therefore, it becomes difficult to utilize this for use in joining with the face plate as in the case of utilizing it as a core-material for a sandwich structural material. Because of this, a plurality of forming stands are used and forming is accomplished by the forming roll, after which a sizing roll or a setting roll may be used to improved a flatness of the wave head and wave bottom.

Fig.9 Location of difficulty in zeta-core forming

Fig.10 Rolls for forming zeta-core

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The purpose of the invention of zeta sandwich is to obtain a structural form which can compete with the honeycomb sandwich in rigidity-to-weight ratio basis by more simple form. The high rigidity, the isotropy of the elastic properties, and the possibility of circulating a fluid within the sandwich, are the principal features of the concept. Furthermore, it is shown that the combination of a flat plate and a zeta-core as a backing sheet results in a two-dimensionally stiffened plate. Recently, the roll forming process has been successfully developed for manufacturing continuously zeta-core from sheet metals of aluminum and steel. It is still in the stage of laboratory test, however, the principal features in the forming process has been revealed and which can provide the sufficient basis for developing the mass production process.

REFERENCES

- 1 Miura,K., "Structural Form and Geometry," Journal of Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences, Vol.19, No.213, Aug. 1971, pp.366-377
- 2 Miura,K. and Sakamaki,M., "Double Corrugation Surfaces for Stressed-Skin Space Structures," Proceedings of IASS Pacific Symposium-Part II on Tension Structures and Space Frames, International Association for Shell Structures, Tokyo and Kyoto, Oct. 1971, published by Architectural Institute of Japan, 1972, pp.609-616
- 3 Miura,K., "Zeta-Core Sandwich---Its Concept and Realization," ISAS Rept. 480, May 1972, Institute of Space and Aeronautical Science, University of Tokyo
- 4 Miura,K., "New Structural Form of Sandwich Core," Journal of Aircraft, Vol.12, No.5, May 1975, pp.437-441
- 5 Miura,K. and Sakamaki,M., "Study on the Zeta-Stiffened Panel---Part 2, 20th Conf. on Structures and Strength, Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences, 1978
- 6 Tanizawa,K., Kikuchi,F. and Miura,K., "Determination of Equivalent Rigidities of a Zeta-Stiffened Panel," Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, Volume 28, University of Tokyo Press, 1980